

GeoMuzik: A Geographic Interface for Large Music Collections

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Abstract

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This report presents the master thesis proposal for a development of an interface for visualization of large music collections. By proposing a new paradigm for navigation and visualization of these collections, we intend to enhance user experience and music discovery. This is achieved by generating a geographic interface to display the music collection contents as if they were spread out in a globe or map. Music collection information is retrieved from widely known web services such as Wikipedia and Last.FM. Content is displayed according to number of plays and genre. Tags retrieved from Last.FM were used to identify different genres for each artist. Music discovery is encouraged by a playlist implementation. Users trace a route in the world map, and through triangulation techniques, GeoMuzik samples the route and retrieves artists and songs that are close to the pathway defined. In order to evaluate the results a survey was applied to a certain number of subjects and its results are presented as part of this piece of work. Conclusions and future work present the impacts obtained from the use of the interface and the possible extensions that would improve this new approach.

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And finally to everyone that enjoys music. This is what it's all about.

DEDICATION

*the fundamental loneliness goes
whenever two can dream a dream,
together. . .*

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

People have always tried to express their thoughts by visual or spoken means facilitating then communication and common understanding. From pictograms through geographic maps until modern visualization interfaces on displays, visualization has highly evolved through time and has improved human's comprehension of facts.

Visualization can be understood as a way “*to form a mental image or vision of some domain*” [27] or “*to imagine or remember as if actually seeing*” [13]. This technique has helped scientists and ordinary people to make a clearer idea of large data sets that could not be analysed as a whole by a human.

In the case of this master thesis, the large data sets used will be large music collections. Mainly how music collections can be visualized using geographic information of its components.

Since the introduction of the MP3 and the wide-spread of the digital audio, music collections have been present in the every-day life of many. As grew the ways of sharing music also grew music collections and organizing so many items became a very difficult task. The organization of music by title, artist and genre became obsolete due to the dynamic characteristic of the collections and new ways of visualizing content were being demanded by listeners.

Different ways of visualizing music collections have led people to develop new services being the most famous the music recommendation one. Either by matching audio similarities between songs[29] or by simply matching genre and location, many solutions have been proposed and applied, most of them with a fair amount of success e.g. Last.FM[4]. “*Computer systems for music visualization that automatically capture and display music structure will enable people to see, and better understand, the structural patterns that they hear.*” [11]

1.1 Motivation

Digital Music Collections turned out to be a trend on the modern World. The introduction of the MP3 technology as well as the widespread of music players supported the appearance and the popularization of these collections. People wearing earphones in the streets and listening to their private music collections became a common scene.

The internet has played an important role for the music collections once that it became the most relevant environment for visualizing, sharing and recommending music. Many different services are now available online, most of them are free and help users in finding new artists and songs as well as recommending music. This latter feature arouse as an important factor to music collections since people started discovering new music through other's music collections.

The online stores helped in popularizing the music recommendation feature by displaying related content together with the artist information. Many have tried to address this problem - using image retrieval, music information retrieval, etc. . . [31] - basically by trying to extract content information and looking for similar pieces. Nevertheless, there is still a gap between these approaches which is formally known as the semantic gap. It consists of finding relationship between pieces according to user's relation to what one listens.

The issue with these approaches is that most of them are based in the song-artist-genre model where basically the relations between the tracks of the collections are defined by comparing these three factors. This, obviously, implies a big limitation to these applications once that artists or tracks relations are much more complex than simple term comparison. Recent research works proved that the comparison of audio features between different tracks yield better results over the matter of comparing and aggregating similar songs [23].

The use of geographical representation has played an important role on the issue of visualization of large collections/data, especially with the improvement of computational processing [33]. Some developments were done based on geographic information, as carried out in [24] where an abstraction of a globe is used to present a music collection organized by audio similarities. The users were able to identify the similarities as well as memorize the position of some tracks in the globe.

1.2 Objectives and Hypothesis

The purpose of this master thesis is to analyze the problem of visualization of large music collections as well as propose a solution using geographical information of the content. Moreover, a detailed description of the technical aspects of the implementation is presented together with the results obtained. A study on previous interfaces for music collection visualization as well as geographic visualization of large data collections is presented and discussed in this piece of work.

The first hypothesis is that simple labels with general information over a track is not enough to describe or identify all the characteristics one is able to bare in mind over a specific track or song.

The second hypothesis is that music collections cannot be visualized or understood by human analysis, rather different visualization interfaces can help humans identifying all the elements of it as well as extracting inherent information of the collection that could not be previously identified.

The third hypothesis is related to geographic information. Humans tend to associate artists to their geographic location. Placing tracks in a globe, apart from helping in the visualization, it helps the user to understand the influence that the physical location has over artists' background and creativity process.

The conclusions and interpretation of the results identifies user's behaviour toward the application as well as analyzes the impact it had as a whole experience.

In order to reach the goals described above a brief review of the state-of-the-art related to music collection visualization and scientific visualization in a general way is presented.

1.3 Methodology

The development of the master thesis starts by the study and revision of the literature over music collections visualization and geographic visualization. A brief revision on information visualization is also provided.

The construction of the visualization interface began with the creation of artist-location search algorithms and research of possible artist location databases. In parallel, the map

generation for the interface was developed. All the implementation was based in a WEB system and therefore takes advantage of the already available WEB-purpose applications and frameworks.

The playlist implementation came afterwards with the usage of polylines. With the route established, a set of artists are retrieved and organized in a list in order to be played to the user.

Once a prototype was ready, the first tests on the application were started and based on the feedback of the first experiments we performed some improvements until the more stable version was established.

A survey or evaluation method was settled in order to assess the different characteristics of the implementation as well as identify its benefits from previous approaches to music collection visualization.

1.4 Thesis outline

This thesis is made of the introduction and 4 chapters. Chapter number 2 focuses on the information visualization problem and its geographical approaches. There is also a state-of-the-art on music collection visualization with geographic means. Chapter 3 focuses on the description of the GeoMuzik interface and the method used to implement the application and its functionalities. The survey and further evaluation of our implementation is described in Chapter 4 as well as the results obtained. Last, but not least, Chapter 5 brings the conclusions and future work.

Chapter 2

VISUALIZATION OF MUSIC INFORMATION

2.1 Visualizing large amounts of data

Visualizing and understanding large amounts of data has never been an easy task for humans. Depending on the way the information is conveyed, our cognitive system is not able to perceive the most important characteristics, especially if there are many different variables included. The majority of the classes of things do not have a natural physical representation and this poses a challenge for us humans to understand and identify behaviours or trends with this sorts of data [17].

Many different areas have made use of data visualization for the sake of better understanding. Pie charts, graphs, bar charts and the other data plotting techniques are the most used ones, especially if the focus is on quantitative data. Nevertheless, when the amount of data is large and the information to be analysed is not measurable, these techniques tend to be obsolete. Moreover, they do not present inherent information of the content that cannot be quantified. Modern visualization techniques, rather than focusing in showing the evident content, they intend to give a different experience to the user, which means presenting content in a different way and also enabling the user to experiment different views of it.

The human visual system is capable of perceiving information preattentively (can be identified in less than 250ms) by identifying different patterns. [20] This can be very useful in order to allow people to identify different objects easily and make a clear distinction between its various different types. Figure 2.1 presents an example of color distinction and how easy it is for one to identify the odd one out.

Not only colors, but also position, length, slope and other perceptual characteristics might be used in an application or visualization tool to identify trends or special cases. This represents a huge advantage over simple text description. Text is not pre-attentive and represent similar concepts in very different ways, which might lead to confusion. Even

Figure 2.1: Different colors help people identify a different pattern.

though, it still is very helpful and used for the description of abstract concepts.

As stated by Plaisant [30], the evolution of tools and approaches related to information visualization is drawing regular users closer to this reality. However, there is still a need for popularizing these kind of approaches and one of the most important factors is to make user testing and be sure that the solution fits the needs for a big part of the target market.

One of the classical success cases of the information visualization comes from the 19th century. John Snow was trying to identify the main source of an epidemic cholera in London. His idea was to draw in the map of the epidemic center tiles according to the number of deaths. This led him to the solution to the case which was a bad water pump [35]. Figure 2.2 illustrates the case.

Cartography has also been affected by the developments in information visualization. As geographers would say, the world of geography is widely complex and broad and this characteristic is very helpful when it comes to the point of visualizing equally complex data. Humans are used to locating cities, roads, objects and other kinds of things in geographical maps.

Govindarajan and Ward proposed in [18] a geographic visualization tool for WEB search engines. They stated that for some of the queries the geographic information could help users to reduce the search domain, aggregate similar content together and from it obtain more accurate results.

Nongeographical data has been largely represented in cartographical means, as stated by Skupin in [33]. The popularity of the GIS systems developed has also played an important

Figure 2.2: Drawing made by John Snow in the epidemic cholera case.

role since drawing and generating customized maps is no longer a difficult task.

The next sections in this chapter focus on three different approaches using geography as means to visualize music collections. All of them generate a unique map based on content similarity. The data was aggregated together using the machine learning technique Self-Organizing Maps.

2.2 Islands of Music: a success case on geographic visualization

Elias Pampalk, Andreas Rauber and Dieter Merkl proposed a 2D hierarchical model for visualizing music collections based on the Islands of Music [28]. Encouraged by the music recommendation problem, their work is based on identifying audio similarities between different songs and mapping them into a model that would group these songs by genre. The densest regions identify a similar genre and a smaller distance between the songs. A geographic map or Island of Music is plotted based on the 2D model in order to give a better visualization of the collection.

Figure 2.3 depicts the transformation of a data set into a geographic map after having applied the self-organizing map (SOM) algorithm. The data set is composed of hundreds of songs from very different styles. Neighbourhood distances are calculated according to audio

similarities.

Figure 2.3: Geographic Map for Islands of Music. Top-left image shows the original data set and bottom-right image shows the computed geographic map after applying a self-organizing map (SOM) algorithm.

The audio similarities are achieved by applying feature extraction algorithms to a song. The Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) [8] are used to model timbral properties from spectrum models. Since MFCCs are based on time invariant frames, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) [26] are used to model the MFCCs distribution. The similarity between one piece and the other is obtained by comparing the probability of the first piece GMM to have been generated by the second piece GMM. After obtaining the 2D map based on the music collection, as depicts Figure 2.4, a set of labels were distributed along the map in order to help users to find songs more easily.

The regions of the map in dark grey represent great distances between the points. Songs that were placed in this area certainly do not have many similarities. The areas in light grey and white represent a closer match between songs. In general, songs placed in this area belong to the same genre.

The self organizing-maps (SOM), unsupervised neural network, technique was quite successful in aggregating similar songs together; however it was possible to identify that few of the songs were misplaced. Improvements in the audio similarity algorithm could reduce the error level.

Figure 2.4: Island of Music screenshot with labels.

2.3 3D Islands of Music: the evolution

Proposing an evolution to the already famous Islands of Music, the three-dimensional user interface for music collections visualization presents a virtual reality environment augmented with stereo sound. Not only the user is able to navigate through the environment but also hear samples of the songs and visualize the lyrics, pictures and some extra information retrieved from the web. On Figure 2.5, a screenshot is presented of the environment generated.

The environment is generated by computing a self-organizing map (SOM) according to audio similarities present on each song of the collection. Specific features are extracted from the files and are then used to compute the map. Since a SOM by itself is a 2D structure, an approach had to be used in order to generate the height on the map. The Smoothed Data Histogram (SDH) creates a smooth height profile (where height corresponds to the number of items in each region) by estimating the density of the data items over the map [23].

It is also emphasized that audio similarities cannot only be based on audio features comparison since music is always tied to personal and cultural influences that can not be captured by analyzing the audio [23].

Figure 2.5: Three dimensional Island of Music enriched with web information.

Extra information retrieved from the web was introduced to the map in order to display semantic content. This information is extracted by making a query to Google e.g. “artist name” music style. The 100 first results are analyzed and unrelated words are removed by using a previous dictionary with acceptable terms.

The images are retrieved from Yahoo! Image services using a similar technique as the one used for the terms. To find the three most important artists for each cluster, it was basically performed the same ranking method as for the terms [23]. Since this 3D interface is enabled with sound, it actually generates a playlist, differently from the previous approaches that only display playlists.

A small survey was also applied in order to evaluate the interface. Most of the users enjoyed the experience and have not had difficulties in navigating. The images were stated by them as simple gimmick and most emphasized that the display of related words would be a nice feature.

2.4 *Globe of Music*

The Globe of Music project is an evolution toward the Islands of Music project. In this work, a 3D model is proposed for the visualization of the music collection and it has a format of a globe. Using the same organization technique for the songs as in [28], the Globe of Music uses a spherical self-organizing map (SOM) which abolishes the border effect of a regular SOM. The feature extraction technique used was based on Statistical Spectrum

Descriptor (SSD) as evaluated in [25].

For the generation of the globe, an icosahedron-based geodesic dome was used. Increasing the tessellation frequency makes the dome look closer to a globe as in Figure 2.6. To this structure with the SOM technique was given the name of GeoSOM.

Figure 2.6: Icosahedron with tessellation frequency 1 to 4.

After having distributed the data among the globe, the GeoSOM is trained in order to obtain the distance between the vertexes. The process of training a GeoSOM is similar to the process of training a SOM. A self-organizing map is a neural network that is trained without supervision. It is mostly used for neighbourhood calculation.

The 3D model for the globe was obtained using the NASA World Wind GIS, an open source application for drawing globes. Using an XML file, a certain amount of parameters for the globe can be defined such as name, equatorial radius and etc. . . The Globe of Music generated can be visualized in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.7: Globe of Music.

The World Wind globe also enables one to add extra information to it using layers. Icons on certain longitude/latitude coordinates with a defined height above surface, including name, texture, dimension, and a link are the most important attributes used in this implementation. Icons are linked to physical files so the user is able to hear which song is in that coordinate.

The implementation of the Globe of Music was tested by test-users in order to validate the interface. A survey was applied after having spent 15-20 minutes experiencing the interface. Ten out of twelve users agreed that they could notice a certain organization on the songs and that they could identify similarity between the neighbour tracks. It was also possible to notice that the visual information helped users in finding a specific track on the globe.

Chapter 3

GEOMUZYK: PLOTTING MUSIC COLLECTIONS IN A WORLD MAP

Large collections of data, especially when represented in a textual way, gives us the feeling of being lost in the hyperspace [10]. For large music collections the behaviour is exactly the same. If you wonder through a digital music collection of any teenager one will find thousands of music files generally organized in the textual song-artist-genre fashion. How can we then organize this collection in a sort of way that it helps the user to find other songs or artists more quickly? As stated in [7], artist similarities cannot be expressed by only words or textual representation, it would be too limiting taking into account the complexity of one's artistic capacities.

All the work developed beforehand and presented in the previous chapter encouraged us to try a different approach on geographic visualization for large music collections. Instead of generating an automatic and artificial geography the world map would be used in order to try to identify other characteristics or trends that were not previously contemplated.

3.1 The interface - a brief introduction

The concept behind our geographic interface is that geo locating artists in a world map would allow users to picture their music collections and then make decisions of whether to search for similar artists that are closely located or to even search for artists in regions of the world that they don't know any artist.

The GeoMuzik interface, rather than focusing on the song file itself, tries to plot one's music collections by retrieving artist information. In other studies, the artist similarity problem was being solved by measuring co-occurrences from different sources such as playlists or presence of the names of two or more artists in the same WEB page [31]. Ellis *et al.* [14] stated that geographical origin is indeed one of the variables that influences the degree in which one artist is similar to another.

The application was thought to be able to present a music collection according to artist locations, number of plays and genre. Not only visualize, but also interact with it. Users are also able to trace a route in the world map. This pathway will be used to generate a playlist with the artists that are on its borders allowing people to get to know different artists from different parts of the world.

GeoMuzik's current database of artists and its geographic locations is made of 17,843 different artists and 4,838 different geolocations. This amount of data is considerably high and proved to be enough to allow a good user experience with the interface.

3.2 Searching and identifying artist locations

Since our focus is on plotting artists in a world map we had to come up with a feasible and accurate solution for searching and identifying geographic locations for those artists. The use of information from the Web was crucial for us.

Two web services were of great help to the development and establishment of the GeoMuzik interface. Last.FM [4] and Wikipedia [5] are mainly the databases of this application. Google Maps [3] service of finding the exact geographical point for a specific location in the world was also of great help.

In order to retrieve the user's music collection, GeoMuzik queries the history of one's listened songs registered in Last.FM. AudioScrobbler offers a web service in which, given the username, a text list with artist names and play counts for a period of twelve months (one year) is given. Based on this information, GeoMuzik searches its own records in order to find a match for every single entry from the previously received text file. For the positive cases, the artist location is identified and a marker is set on the world map accordingly. Figure 3.2 presents a schematic diagram of this feature.

In case the interface does not know the artist, a special record is kept in its database for a further search of the artist location.

3.3 The quest for geographic locations of unknown artists

Those artists that are yet not geolocalized in GeoMuzik interface will be kept in its database for further investigation. There is a special module in our application that automatically

Figure 3.1: Schematic diagram of the steps taken by GeoMuzik to retrieve a user music collection.

searches for artist locations.

Our source, in this case, is Wikipedia [5]. Since there is no ground truth or an official collaborative geographical location database for artists, we decided to use Wikipedia as it presents a good level of knowledge of various different artist and experience has proved that its data is reliable.

Artist pages in wikipedia follows a standard. On the top right corner of each artist page, general information about one’s biography is presented. Inside this table there are two possible sources of the artist geographic location: *Born* and *Origin*. In case both information is present, our interface gives priority to *Origin* since we believe that one’s origins has more influence on his/hers artistic process than the birthplace. Figure 3.3 presents a screenshot from Wikipedia or an artist page.

The main challenge in this feature was to retrieve with the highest level of accuracy the artist location. As can be seen in Figure 3.3, the *Born* section does not present the artist location, only the birth date. This is not true for all cases. For some artists, the *Born* section not only presents the birth date, but also the birth place. In this specific case for “Etta James”, the application will give priority to the *Origin* section as explained above.

When the data is only presented in *Born* section, the algorithm will retrieve char by char from right-to-left and will stop until it reaches a char that is not in the range from a

Etta James

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Etta James (born **Jamesetta Hawkins** on January 25, 1938) is an American blues, soul, R&B, rock & roll and jazz singer and songwriter. James is the winner of four Grammys, seventeen Blues Music Awards, and was inducted into the Rock & Roll Hall of Fame in 1993, the Blues Hall of Fame in 2001, and the Grammy Hall of Fame both in 1999 and 2008. In the 1950s and 60s, she had her biggest success as a blues and R&B singer. She is best known for her 1961 ballad "At Last", which has been classified as a "timeless classic"^[*citation needed*] and has been featured in many movies, television commercials, and web streaming services since its release.

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Etta James in 1990

Background information	
Birth name	Jamesetta Hawkins
Born	January 25, 1938 (age 70)
Origin	Los Angeles, California, USA
Genre(s)	Blues, soul, R&B, rock & roll, jazz
Occupation(s)	Singer, Songwriter
Years active	1954 – Present

Figure 3.2: Wikipedia page for Etta James.

to z , considering upper and lower cases.

Once the location is retrieved, a query is made to a Google Maps server in order to obtain the latitude and longitude of this specific location.

3.4 Defining genres for artists based on Web retrieved information

The importance of tags and genres relies on our personal perception of different kinds of music. Fast beats, synthesized sounds, electronically modified voice, strong lyrics, etc. . . All these characteristics in a song might define a specific genre according to its cultural background and position in time. The fact is that genres have different meanings for different people, communities and countries [16].

Genres are indeed an important classification for songs and for the reasons mentioned above, it was considered for the GeoMuzik interface as a method to classify artists. Not only experts, but also general users are taking place into the task of defining music genres. Last.FM has become an important source of genres as a Web 2.0 tool.

As an important source of *tags*, Last.FM was chosen as our unique genres' database. *Tagging* is a categorization process that is currently being defined by internet users. Many different web services are allowing their users to tag their content in order to differentiate them and improve searching. This sorts of sets that are defined by *tags* are called "folksonomies" [19].

Table 3.1: List of genres and their corresponding colors in the interface.

Blues	Pink	
Classical	Blue	
Country	Purple	
Electronic	Orange	
Hip Hop	Red	
Jazz	Green	
Latin	Light Green	
Pop	Yellow	
Rock	Dark Blue	
Soul	Grey	
Metal	Black	
Undefined	White	

In our case, the *tags* defined by Last.FM users to artists will be used as a way to categorize them into genres. The relevance of Last.FM tags as means to define genres was analyzed in [34]. Taxonomies defined by specialists were compared to *tags* set by users of the social community and the results presented a common trend between the user defined data and the experts definition. Table 3.1 presents the genres selected and the color mapped to each one of them.

Taking as an example the artist “Amaral”, these are its three most relevant *tags*: *spanish*, *pop* and *spanish pop*. GeoMuzik will make a search on these three *tags* in order to identify a pattern that matches one of its predefined genres. The order matters, since the first *tag* is the most relevant and has been tagged by most of the listeners of the artist. In this case, the genre defined for “Amaral” would be “*pop*” since it is present in the second *tag* and it is more relevant than the third one. This would also be the case if any of the following *tags* has another word that matches one of the predefined genres. The first one will always have the priority.

Figure 3.3: Music Collection of a specific Last.FM user.

Figure 3.4 presents a screenshot of the GeoMuzik interface displaying a music collection identifying genres and resizing markers according to play counts.

3.5 Handling with overpopulated zones

As one can perceive, many artists belong to the same region or city in the world which means that in our database we have more than one artist mapped to the same geographic point. In order to avoid superposition of markers in the map and for the sake of visualization, a small random displacement for every artist marker in the map was introduced. Doing so, we can enable users to visualize dense areas such as New York and London with clarity and

without losing much accuracy.

Figure 3.5 presents a zoom on Hybrid mode of a dense area of the map. In this case it is the region close to London, UK.

Figure 3.4: Zoom of a dense area (London, UK) on Hybrid mode showing small displacements.

3.6 Finding artists and new music by route tracing

Playlist has become a common term for any person that possesses a digital music collection. A playlist is a set of songs aggregated in a sequential order in which these songs might or might not have any relation to each other, even though they usually have.

Many researchers from the Music Information Retrieval field have focused on the automatic generation of playlists. Knees *et al.* [22] proposed an audio-based similarity with web-based data in order to maximize the similarity between all the tracks inside a playlist. They pose that not only audio similarities are important but also rich information added by users to the World Wide Web since music is moved by one's perception of it, not just by its audio characteristics.

A similar approach to our GeoMuzik interface is described in [12]. A simple visualization interface is defined for music collections and users are able to automatically generate playlists. In this case, the process of generating new playlists is defined according to a training set of playlists defined by experts (in this case DJs). The author also stresses that the process of playlist creation shall not be totally automatic and that the influence of the user is highly recommended.

Figure 3.6 presents a schematic diagram of the playlist generation feature.

Figure 3.5: Schematic diagram of the steps taken by GeoMuzik to generate a playlist according to a specified route.

In the case of the GeoMuzik interface, the playlist is generated by tracing a route in the map. The user is able to mark a starting point on the map and from then on trace a route that is drawn whilst the points are selected. After having finished the process, the interface starts the search for artists in the areas close to the route.

Initially, the interface samples each section of two points of the route in ten equal parts. Each point of the sampled parts is then used to look for artists in the database. The points are retrieved by doing a simple mathematic calculation. Firstly, the length of each sector defined by two points from the original route is obtained. This length is then divided by ten in order to obtain the exact distance between the first point of this line (originally clicked by the user) and the first sampled point of the line. The exact coordinates for this first sampled point is calculated by defining a right triangle in which its hypotenuse is the tenth

part of the distance between the two original points. Figure 3.6 presents the right triangle defined by the interface.

Figure 3.6: Right triangle defined by the interface in order to calculate sampled points coordinates.

The angles of the right triangle are obtained by congruence with the bigger triangle created by the two original points defined by the user. With the length of the lines CB , AB and AC (the latter two obtained by subtracting the latitudes and longitudes of the points C and B) one is able to define the cosine and sine of the alpha and beta angles. The coordinates of point D are obtained by identifying the length of the leg ED and the sine of angle alpha.

This process is then repeated for every single sampled point in the original line defined by points C and B .

Having obtained all the sampled points for a specific part of the route, the GeoMuzik interface starts its query for artists that are located either in the exact point or in a region nearby. Figure 3.6 presents an approximation of the area nearby the route that is being considered.

The offset added in order to consider this region is of 0.5 and reaches a maximum of 3 units. The offset is increased every time a query for artists in a specific point or region does not reach the minimum of 3 artists. In case the maximum offset is reached and the limit of 3 artists has not been reached, the interface moves on to the next point and stores on the playlist the artists retrieved so far. The implementation is ready to block possible

Figure 3.7: Route presented as a dark red line and region nearby presented with red transparent squares.

Figure 3.8: XSPF player loading a playlist.

repetition of artists in the same playlist.

Having obtained the whole set of artists for a specific route, the GeoMuzik interface queries a Web service for tracks for those artists. This Web service contains a database of 1.3 million songs distributed among 122,803 artists. A track for a specific artist is chosen at random from the list that is retrieved from the Web service. Finally, the playlist is mounted in a XSPF [6] file and played with a XSPF Flash player [1]. Figure 3.6 presents a screenshot of the XSPF player as it is seen on the interface.

Chapter 4

EVALUATION

Evaluation of user interfaces has been, and still is, a hot topic in the Human Computer Interaction field. Effective methods for evaluation of user interfaces was soon identified as an empirical process but efficient methods for doing so were slow in coming [9].

Among the various different techniques for evaluation, we can cite some of them such as: interviews with users, usability testing, cognitive walkthroughs, heuristic evaluation, etc... [9] All of them present advantages and flaws, it will all depend on which type of interface is being developed and for which purposes. Some of the approaches focus on usability and others in metrics.

These methods for evaluating interfaces are mainly divided into quantitative and qualitative approaches. The former focus on metrics such as the time spent on accomplishing a task, number of tasks, number of mouse clicks and so forth. Quantitative methods try to measure the difference between two different designs and how much one has improved the user experience. The latter, the qualitative one, focus on user experience. Users are encouraged to give their personal feedback regarding their experience using the interface.

Isenberg *et al.* [21] stresses that information visualization solutions shall be evaluated on their real environment and not under controlled procedures in a laboratory. Their proposed grounded evaluation focuses on the qualitative approach since it brings the solution to its real working environment.

The importance of the GIS (Geographic Information System) interfaces and their relevance has led researchers to develop a framework exclusively to evaluate this sort of approaches, as stated in [32]. In this work, the focus is not only on the map but also in other tools that enhance the user experience with the map and that must also be considered.

4.1 *Evaluating GeoMuzik*

For the GeoMuzik interface we focused on a summative evaluation [15] which takes part at the end of the development process. Even though most of the evaluation processes are used whilst the interface is being developed, we decided to evaluate it at the end since we are not only evaluating the interface design (which is not the purpose of this master thesis) but also the scientific knowledge that can be extracted from the usage of the interface.

Both tasks, the music collection visualization and the playlist generation, were evaluated for the GeoMuzik interface. For the first feature our purpose is to check if the new paradigm has reached its goal of facilitating the visualization of the most predominant artists in a user profile. Regarding the second feature, the playlist generation, our goal is to allow users to listen to different artists using a new paradigm based on geographical paths.

The most common way of obtaining user feedback is by making them experience and interact with the interface and then run a poll or survey. In the next sections we describe in details our process of evaluation and present the results obtained.

4.2 *Obtaining user feedback by running a survey*

We have came up with a questionnaire or survey that fits into the structured pattern, which means that the questions are predefined and they usually do not change place from one subject to the other. This, as stated in [15], is a better approach if one intends to compare the results and come up with statistics data at the end. Most of the questions were closed questions and one open question at the end. The closed ones focus on the evaluation by the user of the tasks one was meant to accomplish and the open question at the end focuses on obtaining suggestions and personal feedback.

The first part of the survey intends to identify user's background in music, and music players, and also gathering general information such as gender, age and so forth. We believe that different musical backgrounds yields different user experiences. The second and third part are a set of closed questions based on a 5-point Likert scale in which the user is questioned about the two different tasks mentioned beforehand.

4.3 *Running the experiment*

The experiment was held in two different days and 8 different subjects took part in it. At the beginning of the experiment, without having looked at the interface, they were asked to answer the general questions part. The second part was reading the instructions and performing the first task, which was the visualization of the music collection.

The subjects were encouraged to navigate through the map, identify the different artists by the genre-tags that were shown and verify if they were correctly placed. In general, most of the subjects have not had problems in performing this task and actually enjoyed the experience.

The third part of the experiment was related to the playlist generation. In this part of the interaction, some of the user had some problems. It was not clear for all of them how to trace the route. Some double-clicked the points of the route, some tried to click-and-drag and so forth. Some guidance was provided in order to allow them a proper experience. All of them were able to finish the task successfully.

The survey was the last part of the experiment, after the user tests were finished. No time limits were imposed to the subjects in order to make them more comfortable and perform a better evaluation of the interface. The average time for each one was of 20 minutes. The survey was applied using an open web service called *SurveyGizmo* [2].

4.4 *Results and Discussion*

We first introduce the results by presenting the general characteristics of our group of subjects. Most of them were adults (Figure 4.1(a)), males (Figure 4.1(b)) and with a reasonable musical background (Figure 4.1(c)), with many listening hours per day (Figure 4.1(d)). The music-listening hours per day was all above 2 hours. They were also familiar with the most popular music players available, as presented in Figure 4.1(e). Another important characteristic is how often one updates its music collection through Last.FM, as states Figure 4.1(f). The ones that have not updated their Last.FM account could not proceed with the experiment since the interface could not plot anything.

For us it was important to understand, looking at our general information, that our sub-

Figure 4.1: Subjects’s general information

jects indeed have a good musical background and are familiar to the usual music collection visualization techniques. This enables them to experiment and criticize a new approach, such as GeoMuzik, for music collection visualization.

Regarding the specific information the subjects had to provide about their experience, Figure 4.2 presents the results. A total of 75% of the subjects strongly agreed that the data presented is actually a true extraction of their personal music collection which means that the interface has a very high level of inaccuracy when dealing with artist identification and its geolocation. This can be identified in Figure 4.2(a).

The feedback for the correctness of artists placed in the world map was also positive and 62.5% of the subjects strongly agreed that the artists were correctly placed. Also, 37.5% only partially agreed because some of their artists were badly positioned. This is due to eventual misinterpretations of the information retrieved by GeoMuzik from Wikipedia regarding artist localization. Figure 4.2(b) presents the data.

Regarding the number of play counts for each artist and its relation with the size of the markers, the interface also presented a good result. 62.5% of the subjects strongly agreed that it was correctly identified. The partial agreements of 37.5% of the users is due to the fact that our main source of data from Last.FM caches user information and does not present real-time numbers. Similar results were obtained for the genre identification according to artists *tags*. Figures 4.2(c) and 4.2(d) presents these data.

For the playlist feature, we also had some good results even though it's where we had a bigger criticism. The generation of the playlist by tracing a route was stated as a good approach by the majority of the subjects, as states Figure 4.2(e). Some problems were identified during the tracing of the route. The implementation in some cases was not robust; dense areas, with many artist markers, became a challenge for the users if they wanted their route to pass over them. Zooming could easily solve the problem but it was not intuitive for the users since it requires more mouse clicks.

Moving to the actual playlist generated by the route traced, 50% of the subjects agreed that the artists and songs are indeed related to the route they traced. 25% stated that they did not know for sure—as they did not identify the artists—, and the rest, 25% partially agreed. This is due to the fact that our song retrieving web service has an implementation that looks for artist names that are closer to the one presented. The results can be seen on Figure 4.2(f).

Towards artists recommendation, GeoMuzik made a fairly good job since that, again,

62.5% of the users strongly agreed that the playlist generation has helped them to get to know new artists that were previously unknown. This can be visualized from Figure 4.2(g).

Regarding the geographic aspects of the interface, we asked the subjects before and after the experiment which continents they thought they would have artists placed, and which they actually had artists. It was quite impressive to acknowledge that most of the users have no idea of which parts of the world belong the artists that they listen to. Figure 4.3(a) presents these data. As an example, none subject said that they had an artist in South or Central America. Actually, half of them, had artists that were from a country in South or Central America.

Another interesting conclusion is that all of the subjects, at the end, could remember from where their most listened artists was from. Figure 4.3(b) shows the data plot.

4.5 Subject's personal feedback

The subjects, at the end of the experiment, were encouraged to give their personal opinion over the interface. Most of them focused on giving suggestions for improvements. The only criticism made was regarding the geographic localization of some artists, especially in dense areas such as London, Berlin, New York City, etc. . . One of the users stated: “*Artists in the same city, they are wrong placed or better said not precisely placed. Luciano Pavarotti is not german/french/english/swedish, but just Luciano is a german dj*”.

As explained in chapter 3, GeoMuzik defines artists locations according to the data retrieved from Wikipedia [5]. The data retrieved is not always the exact position of an artist inside a city or a specific region. This can also be caused by the small offset added to every artist location in order to avoid overriding of markers. However we believe, and could confirm with the experiment, that this has not prevented the users from having a good experience with the interface and make their conclusions about it.

Regarding the playlist, some of the subjects suggested that it should take into consideration their music collection data by generating a playlist with the artists that they usually listen and similar ones, thus creating a personalized playlist. Others brought up the real-time variable and wanted the map to move as the playlist advanced on the songs.

We also believe that the playlist should have been presented in a different way in order

to allow users to confirm that the artists that they are listening to actually belong to the region in the world where they have traced the route.

(a) Precision of Music Collection data

(b) Correctness of artist geographic information

(c) Correctness of play counts

(d) Correctness of genres per artist

(e) Playlist tracing

(f) Correctness of generated playlist

(g) Artist recommendation

Figure 4.2: GeoMuzik features's evaluation

(a) Location of most listened artist

(b) Personal impressions of music collection

Figure 4.3: GeoMuzik's geographic evaluation

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

The development of GeoMuzik and its following evaluation made us identify various different contributions extracted from this new paradigm for the visualization of a music collection. The state-of-the-art for techniques on geographic visualization of music collections was presented as well as a brief introduction to general information visualization. The GeoMuzik interface then was thoroughly explained with diagrams and pictures of all its phases and features. At the end of the development process, a survey was ran on 8 different subjects in order to evaluate the interface. The results and its further discussion made us identify various different contributions extracted from this new paradigm for the visualization of large music collections.

Geographic means indeed help users to visualize music related data. This can be concluded by the positive feedback received from all the subjects that took part on the experiment. Most of them were quite curious in the beginning which helped them to seize all the possibilities the geographic interface could give.

Playlist generated by a geographic route resulted very intuitive. The users gave a very positive feedback regarding the generation of a playlist using a geographic route. The majority were very enthusiastic about it and gave many suggestions of enhancements to the feature.

Geographic information is a powerful tool for music recommendation. The world map demonstrated to be a very powerful paradigm once the interface is able to recommend new artists to the user by the playlist generation feature. This can be verified not only by the enthusiasm demonstrated by the subjects, but also for the very positive feedback they gave by stating that the route tracing has indeed helped them to get to know new artists.

Users indeed make associations between artists and physical locations. Most

of the subjects answered that they could indeed remember the geographic position of their most listened artist. This could be also verified when they zoomed to the region their artists belonged to and could verify that some of them were not placed in the specific neighborhood they belong to inside a city or region. Even though this level of accuracy is not the main goal of the interface, it proves that the geographic paradigm introduces new possibilities.

Users do not have a good general idea of their music collection regarding its geographic characteristics. Most of the users failed to identify correctly all the continents that their artists belong to. This encourages us to expand the possibilities of this approach.

The overall results and conclusion were very positive and promising. It makes room for new features and improvements that could lead the interface to the popularization.

5.1 Future Work

Many different possibilities were identified as possible enhancements or new features for the GeoMuzik interface.

Collaborative database. One of the main goals for the GeoMuzik interface would be its establishment as a collaborative database for artists geographic locations since the services that offer this feature today are not focused on this information and are not accurate enough. This could be achieved by adding more interaction to the interface and allowing users to adjust the artists locations in the world map. This would give us more precise data and would enable GeoMuzik to provide trustable information.

Realtime feedback. Some of the subjects that took part on the survey suggested that the interface should offer more realtime features. This was stressed on the playlist feature. As the list evolves and different artists are presented, the world map could change its focus and show a marker stating from where the artists one is listening comes from.

Integration with social networks. GeoMuzik could be easily aggregated as an application to the social networks that are so commonly used today. It would allow users to get to know each others music collection and allow them to share common artists or to even recommend new ones.

Playlist generation according to user profile. The generation of a playlist consid-

ering the most common genre/artists for a user was highly rated by the subjects. This could be achieved by adding machine learning techniques and would enhance the user experience with the playlist generation feature.

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